

**THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN A LITERARY TEXT AND THE READER:
A RE-READING OR DECONSTRUCTION STRATEGY**

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Annotation. *This article reveals the essence of the re-reading or deconstruction strategy based on the multilayeredness of the text. The object of this research is the deconstructive approach to a literary text and its specific features. The article is relevant due to its focus on aspects such as the polyphonic tone, multilayeredness, and the reader's worldview in the text, which remain outside the traditional analysis that focuses on the idea and images of a literary work. The ideas about the impossibility of creating a single interpretation of a literary text are explained in connection with the reader's personality. The literature analysis in the article is based on a scientific-critical approach. The author explains Jacques Derrida's deconstruction strategy in detail, provides general conclusions that cover the essence of the strategy, and emphasizes the need to apply it to modern Uzbek literary criticism.*

Keywords: *text multilayeredness, decoding, deciphering, re-reading, difference, interpretation, binary opposition, rewriting.*

Introduction. In the mid-1960s, a structuralist approach emerged in world literary criticism, positing that the underlying meaning of a text could be discovered through analysis of its inherent structural codes. According to this approach, each text possesses infinite meanings, precluding any definitive interpretation. During the reading process, the reader recodes the text, i.e., it is decoded from the author's code into the reader's text. The author's code inherently disappears within the reader's decoding. In other words, during the reader's decoding process – the process of perceiving the text – the entropy¹ of the author's codes becomes so insignificant that the code of the author's text transforms into the codes of the text perceived by the reader. The word “author” itself becomes insignificant, and the author begins to disappear entirely. One of Barthes' definitions of text was: “Text is an exteriority that remains inside” [6; 25]. This idea can be explained as follows: the text is a visible reality, a phenomenon, but it is not a text in precisely its visible state. That is, the “residue” that remains in the reader's mind after reading the text can be considered the

¹ Entropy (Greek Τροπή – rotation, change) - in thermodynamics - one of the state functions of any thermodynamic system. It expresses the direction in which a process occurs in a closed system left to its own devices (not affected by external forces). 2) in static physics - a quantity expressing the thermodynamic probability of the state of the system.
<https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Entropiya>

real text. This is precisely why the text is an exteriority that remains inside. Furthermore, another of Barthes' definitions of text deserves special attention: "The text – writing – is a novel without a novel, a poem without a poem, an essay without an essay, writing without style, production without product, structure without structure" [6; 22]. This very sentence fully demonstrates the new approach to literature presented by Barthes. This idea, based on Barthes' research, can be explained as follows: the text is rewritten by the reader while reading, therefore the text becomes an infinite writing – each reader recreates the text in their own way; this process continues even when only one reader of the text remains. Therefore, we cannot fit it into literary-theoretical frameworks; it is impossible to evaluate the text as a poem or a novel, because it exists with a separate structure in the mind of each reader. To fully comprehend these reflections, the re-reading strategy developed by the French scholar Jacques Derrida becomes important. The discussion section of the article will attempt to explain the essence of this strategy.

Research Methods. The article utilizes methods of analysis, synthesis, and discussion in analyzing and summarizing scientific literature. The comparative analysis method was also employed to compare the views of theorists and arrive at a general and objective conclusion.

Results and Discussions. In a thorough structural analysis of a literary text, the process of deciphering – revealing the meaning of the codes in the text – is of great importance. This process, in turn, occurs as a result of penetrating into the deeper layers of the text. Barthes calls this phenomenon "re-reading": "Indeed, re-reading is the work of language (the system in the mind). Reading is identifying meanings, and identifying meanings leads to renaming them; but the point is that these renamed meanings aspire to other names, so that names begin to echo each other, group together, and these groups again require naming: I name, I choose names, I name again, and this, in fact, is the life of the text: this is nomination, a continuous approximation process. Re-reading is an activity that contradicts the commercial and ideological habits of our society; the above habits recommend that after reading this or that story, immediately "throw it away" and take a new one, recommend buying another book for yourself. We recognize the right to re-read for certain categories of readers (children, the elderly, and teachers); we propose to consider re-reading as a basic principle, because only it can protect the text from repetition (people who ignore re-reading are forced to read the same story from any text)" [6; 27]. Given the multi-layered nature of a text, it is necessary to cultivate the habit of re-reading to comprehend its deepest layer. Only then will you feel the unique textual beauty inherent in each text; otherwise, if you are content with the surface layer, even if you read diverse works of world literature, be it genre, ideological, or stylistic, you will still not be able to overcome the author's barrier.

Re-reading should take the text beyond the boundaries of time and space, freeing it from any external connections. Only the text and the reader, nothing and no one else! The true text, as Barthes emphasized, is written while being read in this environment. This is where the beauty and power of a literary text lie. The text continuously transforms into a unique phenomenon for each reader, each reader re-discovers it based on their personality, knowledge, and worldview. For this, the text needs to be read not once, but repeatedly, only then can the reader overcome the initial reading stereotypes. This, in turn, lays the foundation for the formation of a new reading culture. To enjoy reading examples of contemporary world literature where personality is a pressing topic, this very deconstruction strategy is needed.

Barthes dwells deeply on the method he called “re-reading” and Derrida calls it “deconstruction strategy”. First, let’s look at the explanation of this term: The word “deconstruction” comes from the French “déconstruction”, which consists of two parts: “dé” (out, removal) and “construction” (building, creation). It is mainly used in the context of postmodernism and philosophy. This method aims to analyze the internal structure of texts or ideas and free them from traditional concepts. The deconstruction methodology helps to divide a text or theory into several layers and reveals the contradictions within it. In general, deconstruction is the process of revising the uniqueness or rules of something, and it is often used to criticize traditional thinking and introduce a new point of view. In his research [2], Derrida considers the new reading approach, which he calls deconstruction, as the only correct and purposeful strategy. Literary critic Charles E. Bressler, writing about the characteristics of a literary text in his book “Literary Criticism: An Introduction to Theory and Practice”, also touches upon Derrida’s deconstruction theory: “...it is not a methodology, nor is it a theory, but rather an approach to literature, a strategic tool” [1; 117]. We also believe that deconstruction is a strategy that encourages the reader to rise to a higher level. In his teaching, Derrida puts forward the idea that the true owner of the text is the reader, and based on this idea, he comes to the conclusion that since the text is under the judgment of the reader, not the author, then it is impossible to speculate on its final analysis. Derrida begins his explanation of his new reading strategy by analyzing Ferdinand de Saussure’s “Course in General Linguistics” [3, 8]. Derrida accepts Saussure’s hypothesis about the arbitrary and conventional nature of the linguistic sign. He also emphasizes that the linguistic sign consists of two parts: the “signifier” and the “signified”, i.e., the concept expressed through the sign. For Saussure, the meaning within the language resides in the systematized combinations of sounds created on the basis of the differences of signs, which does not depend on the internal properties of the signs. This concept – that the meaning in the essence of language is determined by the differences between the signs – serves as an important foundation for Derrida’s

deconstruction theory. To gain a clearer understanding, we will explain this idea using the example of the phoneme-sound opposition: sound combinations arise based on the differences of signs in a phoneme. For example, in the language system, the phoneme [a] has various forms in speech, and naturally, there are certain specific differences between them: qarz (hard “a” pronunciation), sahih (soft “a” pronunciation), tabiat (narrow “a” pronunciation), ota (wide “a” pronunciation),... Thus, certain contradictory differences in the sound combinations that emerge as a realization of the phoneme [a] constitute the true essence of the phoneme. Derrida’s deconstruction strategy relies on these very ideas put forward by Saussure – the true essence of any text, its inter-layered meaning, is formed only on the basis of the differences in its reader-read versions, the contradictions that these differences reveal.

Conclusions. After studying Jacques Derrida’s research, we focused on the following as the main principles of deconstruction:

1.The Interconnection of Meaning and Text: Derrida emphasizes that meaning is always changeable and dependent on the text. He argues that meaning cannot be limited to anything, and therefore it is impossible to create a single and final analysis of the text. A true text should not have boundaries of time, space, and, along with that, the author. Each text should have thousands of interpretations in the minds of readers, and this situation is quite natural for structuralism.

2.Binary Opposition: Derrida proposes to deconstruct the oppositions that exist in traditional philosophy (e.g., subject and object, material and spiritual). He demonstrates, using the example of a literary text, that these oppositions actually complement each other and are interconnected.

3.The Concept of Différance: Derrida introduces the term “différance” (differing, deferral), which implies that the text does not have a final meaning and that each text gains meaning through other texts. This concept shows that meaning is not a static, but a dynamic process. The significance of différance is that when you are reading a text, that very text no longer exists. Since all meanings and knowledge are based on differences, a text cannot mean only one thing; texts are in an intertextual state. The meaning of one text comes from the interrelationship of many other texts. According to the essence of this term, no one can recognize one interpretation of the text as correct or say that another interpretation is incorrect; because the meaning in the text is always in motion, dynamic and temporary.

4.Reading and Interpretation: Deconstruction in the reading process is not limited to the surface meaning of the text. Rather, it makes it necessary to divide the text into layers and to be able to grasp the underlying meaning between the layers. In this regard, the reader's thinking, worldview, knowledge, and experience play an important role.

5. Rewriting: In Derrida's theory, the deconstruction process is carried out by rewriting existing texts and considering them in new contexts. This happens only in the reader's mind. As long as the text has a reader, the deconstruction process never stops.

If Derrida's re-reading strategy is applied to the analysis of modern and postmodern literary examples being created as a product of renewed thinking, it will initiate a new stage of literary criticism, and indeed, readership, in Uzbek literary studies. If scientific research related to a literary text is based on this new approach, it will be easier to draw an objective conclusion. This will contribute to further raising the status of Uzbek literature on the world stage of literature and literary criticism.

References:

1. Bressler, Charles E. *Literary Criticism and Introduction to Theory and Practice*. New Jersey: Pearson Education, 2007. – P.118.
2. Derrida, Jacques. "Structure, Sign, and Play in the Discourse of the Human Sciences" in *The Languages of Criticism and the Sciences and The Sciences of Man: The Structuralist Controversy*. eds. Richard Macksey and Eugenio Donato. Maryland: John Hopkins University Press, 1970.
3. Ferdinand de Saussure. *Cours de linguistique générale*. Wiesbaden, Harrassowitz, 2, 1968. -P. 272.
4. Rasulov A. *Struktura va strukturalizm*. – Manba: Rasulov A. Badiiylik – bezavol mezon. – Toshkent: "Sharq" nashriyot-matbaa aksiyadorlik kompaniyasi bosh muharririyati, 2007.
5. Semih Gümüř. *Modernizm ve Postmodernizm*. Istanbul.,2021.
6. Барт Ролан .S/Z (перевод с французского Г. К. Косикова и В.П.Мурат). — М.: Эдиториал УРСС, 2001. – С.25
7. Барт Р. *Избранные работы. Семиотика. Поэтика*. – Москва, Прогресс, 1989.
8. Соссюр Фердинанд де. *Курс общей лингвистики*. Пер. с французского. М.: Эдиториал УРСС, 2004. — 256 с.
9. Лотман Ю.М. *Структура художественного текста*. – Москва: Искусство, 1970. – 371 с.
10. <https://coollib.net/b/194994-ilya-petrovich-ilin-poststrukturalizm-dekonstruktivizm-postmodernizm/read>
11. <https://www.thecollector.com/jacques-derrida-postmodernism/>
12. <https://literariness.org/2019/04/17/the-philosophy-of-jacques-derrida/>
13. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rolan-bart-tekst-i-zhizn>
14. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rolan-bart-paradigma-neytralnoe-dao>
15. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/taynaya-zhizn-slov-literaturnaya-teoriya-rolana-barta/viewer>